

Analytical and experimental study on high-temperature high-velocity impact limit for C/C composite

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Analytical modeling

The penetration process was governed by the conservation law of energy

$$m_p V_p^2 / 2 = m_p V_f^2 / 2 + m_r V_r^2 / 2 + m_t V_t^2 / 2 + W_l + W_f$$

$$W_l = \int_0^{t_w} \frac{t_w}{\cos \theta_p} A_h \sigma \left(\frac{t_w}{\cos \theta_p} - x \right) dx = \frac{\pi d_h t_w^2 \sigma}{2 \cos^2 \theta_p}$$

$$W_f = m_p m_w V_p^2 / 2 (m_p + m_w)$$

$$m_p V_p \cos \theta_p = m_p V_f \cos \theta_f + m_t V_t \cos \theta_t - m_r V_r \sin \theta_r$$

$$m_p V_p \sin \theta_p = m_p V_f \sin \theta_f + m_t V_t \sin \theta_t + m_r V_r \cos \theta_r$$

$$\frac{m_t}{m_p} = -0.433 \left(\frac{t_w}{d_p} \right)^{0.605} \left(\frac{V_p}{C_w} \right)^{0.112} \cos^{-1.693} \theta_p + 1.065$$

$$\frac{\theta_t}{\theta_p} = 0.471 \left(\frac{t_w}{d_p} \right)^{-0.054} \left(\frac{V_p}{C_w} \right)^{-0.049} \cos^{1.134} \theta_p$$

$$V_t \cos \theta_t = V_f \cos \theta_f$$

$$V_f = \left(m_p V_p - m_t V_t + \sqrt{m_r V_r^2 - 2 m_r \cdot W_s} \right) / m_p$$

$$m_t = 0$$

$$m_r = m_w = \pi d_{hc}^2 t_w \rho_w / 4$$

$$m_p = \pi d_{pc}^3 \rho_p / 6$$

$$V_r = V_p \times \left[-0.514 \times \left(t_w / d_{pc} \right)^{0.679} \times \left(V_p / c_w \right)^{-0.064} \times \cos^{-0.936} \theta_p + 1.046 \right]$$

**Critical projectile diameters d_{pc} could be obtained as function of the impact velocity V_p .
** This characteristic curve of ballistic limit could be used to predict the penetration performance of structures.
** The analytical model was valid for thin target panels and the cases where the ricochet debris cloud caused by the projectile couldn't be ignored.

Experimental test

Test results

NO.	Projectile diameter (mm)	Projectile material	Impact angel (degree)	Panel material	Panel thickness (mm)	(m/s)	(°C)	Test result*	d (mm)	Elliptical hole size # (mm)	
										a	b
1	2	Si ₃ N ₄	45	SiC-C/C	5	1340	815	Perf	--	8.55	6.22
2	3	Si ₃ N ₄	45	SiC-C/C	5	2230	1420	Perf	--	15.16	12.60
3	2	Si ₃ N ₄	15	SiC-C/C	5	2740	1430	Perf	28	10.45	9.85
4	2	Si ₃ N ₄	30	SiC-C/C	5	2390	1206	Perf	--	10.70	9.15
5	3	Si ₃ N ₄	30	SiC-C/C	5	2970	830	Perf	30	14.05	14.90
6	3	Si ₃ N ₄	15	SiC-C/C	5	1490	1232	Perf	--	9.25	10.90
7	5	Si ₃ N ₄	45	SiC-C/C	5	2820	1205	Perf	20	23.43	19.93
8	5	Si ₃ N ₄	30	SiC-C/C	5	1760	1401	Perf	44	17.30	15.15
9	5	Si ₃ N ₄	15	SiC-C/C	5	2570	822	Perf	15	18.96	18.30
10	3	steel	15	SiC-C/C	5	2990	1229	Perf	23	13.92	13.83
11	3	steel	15	SiC-C/C	5	3130	1267	Perf	27	14.76	14.68
12	3	steel	15	SiC-C/C	5	2720	18	Perf	25	16.28	15.62

Schematics of the impact facilities (a) Two-stage light gas gun (b) Impact setup in light gas gun impact chamber (c) C/C specimen

Discussion

Target

Witness plate

Comparisons of analytical and experimental results of projectile deflection angle

A general guideline is provided with the proposed analytical model and the experimental data on designing the TPS of the spacecraft structures, considering the effects of the impact pairs, impact velocity, impact angle, working temperature and projectile diameter.

- The distribution of post-impact fragments and trajectory of unbroken projectiles through the hypervelocity impact process are considered phenomenologically when establishing the analytical model, and the new model could provide a more accurate prediction than the tradition one available in open literature.
- Comparison of the trajectory of projectile predictions and data from experimental test program in this paper shows a good agreement in both tendency and magnitude.